

INFLUENCE OF SCHOOL EMPLOYEES' BEHAVIOUR ON STUDENTS' COMPLIANCE TO SOCIETAL NORMS IN SELECTED UNIVERSITIES IN OGUN STATE NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Inability to comply to societal norms has brought some negative influences on the total life of students, which directly and indirectly affect the country's economy. Therefore, this study assessed the influence of school employee's behaviour on students' compliance to societal norms in selected Universities in Ogun State. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey design and used a multi-stage sampling technique to select the 393 participants for this study. The information collected from the respondents were sorted, coded, using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics of frequency distribution mean and standard deviation was used to analyse the data and provide answers to the research questions. Multiple regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses at 5 percent level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) The results of this study revealed that there is no significant influence of school employees' behaviour on students' compliance to societal norms in the selected universities ($\beta = .038, t = .755, f = 0.570, p = .451 > .05$). The study further revealed a significant influence of school employees' behaviour on students' honesty ($\beta = .115, t = 2.281, f = 5.202, p = .023 < .05$) and moral ($\beta = .106, t = 2.098, f = 4.401, p = .037 > .05$). The study concluded that whatever change we expect in our students behaviour must start from the staff and significant others. It was recommended that parents and guardians should bridge up the communication gaps between them and their youngsters so as to understand and appreciate their nature, aspirations and yearnings. This will help in accommodating them and assist them in channeling their behaviour on the right paths.

Keywords: Employees' Behaviour, Students Compliance and Societal Norms

Introduction

Nigeria society have norms, values, principles, morals and cultural ethics which the people conform to and in relation to one another. There are diverse ethnic groups in Nigeria. The norms were appreciated among Nigerian people across the geographical regions, among the people and culture. These values, principles, and morals are transferred from one generation to

another. Okobia, and Okafor (2016) state that societal norms compliance creates a peaceful and conducive environment within the economic life, and in the industrial activities of Nigerian. The social group addresses behavioural issues and discipline individuals who go contrary to the rules and regulations. The Obas or the leaders of the society are saddled with the responsibility of ensuring that the culture, the rules and regulations are preserved. Okobia, and Okafor (2016)

Strickland (2018) stated that A norm is a standard or pattern of behaviour that is considered desirable within a society or group of people in a community. It represents what is the 'normal' way of behaving in a given context. While behaviour encompasses the actual actions and conduct of individuals or group in a given society. Chineyemba, (2023) stated that good parents do not always produce good children, but devoted, dedicated, hardworking mothers, and fathers can weigh the balance in favor of decency and moral character woven into the behaviour of a child. This determines how well that child will fit into the society. Chineyemba, (2023) further claimed that Nigerians believed that wealth comes from hard work. People who possessed wealth that could not be accounted for was viewed with suspicion, the community frowns at such a person. The value of wealth is linked with accountability and transparency. It is also believed that people cannot be poor when they are hardworking (Abiona, 2016).

Regarding conduct of members of the society, Ocheje, (2017) maintained that the factors constraining the effectiveness of justice in the fight against corruption has to do with compliance to the laws. The society is moving toward freedom for individual sexual gratification and all manners of sexual self-expression that negates the acceptable standard. This has led to the prevalence of underage children becoming mothers; this has pervaded our societal moral values. Chineyemba, (2023) ascertained that dignity of labour as a cherished value has been infested with corrupt virus of quick way to success as no one wants delay in success.

The success highway code does not include hard-work anymore for most people. This accounts for the thriving illegal business called '419, Yahoo yahoo' or internet fraud and the like. Academic praise among students has become a thing of past. There are organized crimes, in our ivory towers, an organized examination by the principal or proprietor of the school to influence the enrolment. Miracle Centre Syndrome (MCS) where candidates pay exorbitantly to people who help them write their examinations is eroding the value of study has eroded the educational system of her pride. The government is not free from this allegation of erosion of our values. Insincerity, dishonesty, unfaithfulness, cheat, corruption, bribery, favoritism, irresponsibility, irresponsiveness, pen-robbery, embezzlement, harassment, organized crime and gambling, deceit, lies, exploitation, and more, have characterized the activities of the government because moral principles are no longer recognized in our country (Abiona,et..al , 2016).

Schools are the nursery of the state and where students spend most of their time. Belle (2017) observed that overpopulated learning environment; violent discipline measures from school heads; incompetent school administrators and faculties; lack of freedom to choose what course to study; discrimination; poor association from friends and corrupt teachers; are some of the factors militating against students' inability to comply to societal norms (Belle, 2017).

It is common knowledge that students are not identical in behaviors, opinions, and views. (Dagdag 2018) noted that students vary regarding physical, intellectual, social-emotional, moral, spiritual, and cultural background. There is need for teachers to acquire more skills, knowledge and values as the demand of their task and responsibilities increases, hence it is expected that

school employees inculcate the consciousness of moral values, principles, honesty, discipline, responsibility that will enhance holistic education to student as they progress in their academic pursuit (Aslam, Mohammed & Muhammad 2021).

Employee behaviour is embedded in both positive and negative behaviours. Every employee is expected to be faithful in the discharge of their responsibility. Honesty, punctuality, and regularity to work are virtue expected of school employee. Diligence in the discharge of responsibilities cannot be overemphasized. The above virtues can be listed among the positive behaviour of school employees. On the other hand, employees can display negative behaviour such as lying, lateness to work, absenteeism, stealing of the school property, dishonesty, bribery and corruption, which affect negatively affect the image of the school (Obijuru, Oguejiofor & Emenike, 2017).

Standards for healthy living create a good sense of atmosphere in the school environment. This healthy living build on rules or principles create a harmonious society, for this reason schools executives set expectations about acceptable behaviour. A positive behaviour toward maintaining high standards for work ethics usually creates a decent environment in which people take pride in the work; parents, students and community derive joy to belong. Duggan (2023) states in contract of employment there is this relationship that employers have the obligations to pay the employee agreed pay for duties and activities performed and to provide employee with job activities intellectually. School managers and educational personnel look at an employee's behavior to determine his or her ultimate productivity and contributions to the school or management objectives. In many cases, a person's behaviour is affected by his attitude.(Leonard, 2018).

Bureau (2023) School Administration Guide sees compliance as having to do with students actually obeying the rules and working towards achieving the behavioural goals factored in the rules and regulations. This principle of life virtue known as honesty and moral behaviour has been studied by other scholars. Tawiah, Amuah, Appiah, & Annan, (2022), in their study affirmed that honesty and dishonesty:, trustworthiness, frankness, authenticity, integrity, candour, probity, rectitude and incorruptibility just to mention a few. The study also revealed that, some students were found not to be honest (cheating in examination, leaving school without exeat, covering up for wrongdoing, not obeying schools' rules and regulations and so on. Employers can promote good employee behaviour with incentives. The work also revealed that in a school setting employer can contribute to positive or negative attitude in employees using incentives.

Concept of school Employee Behaviour

In every educational system, school employee is core because it is important as the establishment of the institution itself. The need for human engagement in various capacities is inevitable hence the human capital is the key to the success of educational goal achievement. School is an arena in which a variety of behaviours play out, each with a different consequence for the individuals within the organization and on the organization as a whole. Every organization has its norms and expected behaviours, language, principles and postulations by its

members, and also the employees that are in the workplace to perform at a suitable pace in order to achieve the organization's goals and objectives (Abiona et al., 2020).

Biscobing (2016) concept of compliance as a state of either being in accord with established guidelines, rules or specifications, or the process of becoming towards others and having Social norms dictate the extent to which individuals engage, and expect others to engage in some acts. Telzer (2018) maintains that people are strongly influenced by social norms even when they explicitly reject such norms, also Brennan, Eriksson, Goodin, and Southwood (2020) argue that norms have a function. Norms function to hold us accountable to each other for adherence to the principles that they cover.

Statement of Problem:

Inability to conform to societal norms has brought some negative influences on the moral life of students. These immoral behaviours directly affect the country's economy. Also, foreign investors find it scary to invest in the economy of the country because of the deplorable level of immoral and dishonesty in the country. This study aimed to examine the influence of school employees on students' compliance to societal norms in three selected Universities in Ogun State.

Objectives of the Study

The major objective of the study was to examine the influence of school employee's behaviour on students' compliance to Honesty and Moral in selected Universities in Ogun State. The specific objectives are to:

ascertain the influence of school employees' honesty on student compliance to societal norms in the selected Universities

determine the extent to which school employees' morals influence students' compliance to societal norms in the selected Universities

Research Hypotheses

Ho1: There will be no significant influence of School employees' honesty on students' discipline selected Universities.

Ho2: There will be no significant influence of school employees' moral on students' compliance to societal norms moral

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive research design using the survey which enable the researcher to collect data from a sample of the targeted population without manipulating either of the independent or dependent variables but measuring them as they existed among the participants in this study.

Population

The population of this study is 24000 students from the three selected universities in Ogun State. Which are as follows: Onabisi-Onabanjo University Ago-Iwoye State University, University of Agriculture Abeokuta and Babcock University Ilishan Remo. With the stratum of 300L and 400L female and male students of the three selected Universities which are considered as the respondents. This level of students were used for the study in order to reduce the difficulties that may associate with large population study.

Instrumentation

The following instrument was used for data collection in this study:

Demographic Data Inventory (DDI), School Employees' Behaviour Questionnaire (SEB Q) and Societal Norm Compliance Questionnaire (SNCQ)

The Demographic Data Inventory (DDI) is a four-item instrument developed by this researcher to measure the demographic such as age, gender, level and university.

SECTION A

This section elicited responses on demographic variables of participants like such as Sex, age, level and university.

SECTION B

This section measures school employees' behaviour

Section B: Statement: from Higher Extent (5) High (4) Low Extent (3) Lower Extent (2) No Extent (1). Was used to assess the influence of school employees' behaviour on student compliance to societal norm by students of the three universities in Ogun State using the employees.

Section B1: Employees' Honesty

This section measures the influence of school employees' behaviour on students' compliance to societal norms. It is self-constructed by the researcher. It consist of 5 items on a 5 scale Likert-style response ranging from Higher Extent (5) High(4) Low Extent(3) Lower Extent (2) No Extent (1).

Section B2: Employees' Moral behaviour

This section tries to elicit information from students on the academic and non-academic staff behaviour to societal norms Compliance. It consist of 5 items on a 5 scale Likert-style response ranging from Higher Extent (5) High(4) Low Extent(3) Lower Extent (2) No Extent (1).

Section C 1

This section measures students' honesty.

This section measures Students' behaviour on honesty. It is self-constructed by the researcher. It consist of 5 items on a 5 scale Likert- style response ranging from Strongly agree with 5points to undecided with 1 point.

SECTION C1: students' moral.

This section elicited information from the students on their **moral** norms. It consist of 5 items on a 5 scale Likert- style response ranging from Higher Extent (5) High(4) Low Extent(3) Lower Extent (2) No Extent (1).

SECTION C2: Students' moral

This section tries to elicit information from students on their moral. It consist of 5 items on a 5 scale Likert- style response ranging from Higher Extent (5) High(4) Low Extent(3) Lower Extent (2) No Extent (1).This section contains the presentation and interpretation of results of data analysis. Preliminary analyses were conducted on data using descriptive statistics as presented in Tables 1 to 4.

The result of the analysis of the demographic variable as regards the gender of the respondents reveal that 237 (60.3%) were female and 157 (39.7%) were male. In terms of age, 292 (74.3%) aged 21-24 years, 53 (13.5%) aged 16-20 years, and 48 (12.2%) aged between 25 and 29 years.

Results:

Hypothesis One: There will be no significant influence of school employees' behaviour on students' honesty in the selected Universities

Table 1: Summary of Analysis of variance on influence of school employees' behaviour on students' honesty in the selected Universities

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	p-value
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	13.919	1.556		8.945	.000
Employees beh.	.050	.022	.115	2.281	.023
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	91.470	1	91.470	5.202	.023 ^b
Residual	6875.125	391	17.583		
Total	6966.595	392			

R = .115, R Square = .013, Adj. R Square = .011, SE = 4.193

a. Dependent Variable: Students honesty

b. Predictors: (Constant), Employees behavior

Employees' behaviour has a beta value of .115 and t-value of 2.281 significant at .023 alpha level. The calculated value of $f = 5.202$ significant at $.023 < .05$ alpha level indicated a significant influence of school employees' behaviour on students' honesty in the selected Universities. Therefore, the earlier set null hypothesis was rejected while the alternate one was accepted. The implication of this result is that school employees' behaviour will have an influence on the honesty behaviour or attitude of students in the universities.

Hypothesis Two: There will be no significant influence of school employees' behaviour on students' moral in selected Universities

Table 2: Summary of Analysis of variance on influence of school employees' behaviour on students' moral in the selected Universities

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	p-value
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	12.301	1.352		9.099	.000
Employees beh.	.040	.019	.106	2.098	.037
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	58.418	1	58.418	4.401	.037 ^b
Residual	5189.801	391	13.273		
Total	5248.219	392			
R = .106, R Square = .011, Adj. R Square = .009, SE = 3.643					

a. Dependent Variable: Students moral

b. Predictors: (Constant), Employees behavior

Employees' behaviour has a beta value of .106 and t-value of 2.098 significant at .037 alpha level. The calculated value of $f = 4.401$ significant at $.037 < .05$ alpha level indicated a significant influence of school employees' behaviour on students' moral in the selected Universities. Therefore, the earlier set null hypothesis was rejected while the alternate one was accepted. The implication of this result is that school employees' behaviour will have an influence on the moral behaviour or attitude of students in the universities.

Conclusion

Within the academic community, social norms have a significant impact on how students, teachers, and other stakeholders interact and behave. These standards are a collection of unspoken guidelines and expectations that direct behavior, interaction, and communication within the educational setting.

As Nigeria continues to struggle with quality education and degree attainment, higher education administrators and policymakers seek additional evidence on the strategies and interventions designed to improve students' behavioral outcomes. This study provided a critical examination of the research on the influence of school employee's behaviour on students' compliance to societal norm.

The results of this study showed that school employees' behaviour has a significant influence on students' compliance to societal norms in the selected universities. However, employees' behaviour was found to have an influence on students' honesty and moral behaviour.

It is therefore concluded that whatever change we expect in our students behaviour must start from the staff and significant others. Since, societal norms emphasized the ability to understand the values in society about the views of good-bad, right-wrong, what individuals should and should not do in community group, it is therefore important for every parents and leaders act right in all their doings.

Recommendations

In the light of these findings, the following recommendations are hereby made towards solving the problems identified in this study.

Public enlightenment programmes should be mounted by the government [Federal, State and Local] to broaden the knowledge of the populace especially parents and significant others to understand what lies behind compliance to societal norm, young people's risk-taking behaviour and social support outside the family.

Parents and guardians should bridge-up the communication gaps between them and their youngsters so as to understand and appreciate their nature, aspirations and yearnings. This will help in accommodating them and assist them in channeling their behaviour into the right paths. Parents and teachers should also serve as good models and see to the needs of the youngsters.

It is equally recommended that educational needs in Nigeria should be comprehensively reviewed towards meeting the demands of the citizens. Training programmes should be directed at improving the students' overall life engagement in Nigeria.

It may be important to include in addition to other academic trainings, programmes aims at helping students develop emotional intelligence and resilient behaviour to enable them become a better being.

It is recommended that emotional intelligence study should be incorporated into the curriculum of the schools across the federation. In this regard, competent psychologists should be involved in the review of the curriculum for education in Nigeria.

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